

SPIDER VEIN TREATMENT: WHICH ONE TO CHOOSE SCLEROTHERAPY OR COMPRESSION STOCKINGS?

If you have only a couple of problem areas and they do not cause any discomfort or bother appearance-wise, you might not need **vein treatments**. However, if they are problems that spoil your look and cause discomfort, the wisest thing will be to seek out an appropriate form of [spider vein treatment](#).

Compression stockings:

The first thing your doctor might recommend is to start wearing compression stockings. Moreover, he/she may recommend a lifestyle change that can be beneficial for those who have a minor issue in this area. The options in compression stockings include support pantyhose, over-the-counter gradient compression pantyhose, and gradient compression pantyhose that are only available through a **vein doctor near me Clifton** prescription.

Sclerotherapy:

The most used spider vein treatment is known as sclerotherapy. Basically, this method is performed with an injection. The **vein specialist near me NJ** uses a special needle to inject a chemical into the skin for this exact purpose. The chemical causes the walls to begin to

swell. From there the walls glue together and end up sealing shut. This ceases the blood flow, and from there, scar tissue will arise and heal.

After a few weeks have gone by, the treated spot should show signs of fading, which is exactly what is supposed to happen. This spider **vein treatment woodland park** does not necessitate the administration of anesthesia. It does not have to take place in the hospital but can take place right in the doctor's office. Shortly after the **vein treatment Paramus**, the patient will be able to return to their regular activities, including work and school.

An influenced region may just require one injection, yet it might be dealt with more than once by the specialist. If you require more than one **vein treatment NJ**, you will have to schedule them every four to six weeks. Following sclerotherapy, **vein doctor Clifton** may recommend that you wear gradient compression stockings to facilitate the healing process and to minimize any swelling that might take place. This form of spider [vein treatment near me NJ](#) is used all of the time and is highly successful when it is performed properly.

As with any procedure done to the human body, there are possible side effects to think about. Be aware, though, that the advantages of having sclerotherapy far outweigh the disadvantages.

If you have this procedure, you may notice raised, red patches on the treated site, that might even sting. You might even develop bruises where the needle entered your skin. This is temporary and will not take long to go away.

Around the section of skin that has been treated, groups of fine red blood vessels might appear. You also might notice brown lines or spots. These are symptoms that will start to disappear shortly after the therapy has been completed.

Although it is rare, sometimes lumps of blood can become trapped in a treated vein and can become inflamed. The swelling can be relieved by applying heat to it and taking an over-the-counter remedy such as aspirin prescribed by a **vein doctor near me NJ**. When you visit a **vein doctor near me in New Jersey** during the next session, the blood that is trapped will be drained by way of a tiny pinprick.